

A new euphane triterpene and a lipid constituent from the bark of *Boswellia serrata*[†]

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Abstract : The structure of two new compounds isolated from the bark of *Boswellia serrata* have been elucidated to be 20,24-dihydroxyeupha-2,8,22-triene (1) and 5(6)-ene,26-hydroxyoctacosanoic acid (2). The known compounds isolated have been identified as α -amyrenol, β -sitosterol and acetyl β -boswellic acid.

Keywords : Triterpene, lipid constituent.

Boswellia serrata (Burseraceae) is well known for its medicinal properties. The oleo gum resin exudates from it is used as incense and reputed to possess therapeutic properties^{1,2}. In Aurvedic system of medicine it is used as cure for rheumatoid arthritis. The resin obtained from tree is one of the oldest fragrant and medicinal resin, known through out the world. We report herein the isolation and characterization of two new compounds from hexane extract of the bark of the plant.

Results and discussion

Compound 1 was obtained as colorless viscous mass. It showed a molecular ion peak at m/z 440 in the EIMS along with its FAB-MS ion at m/z 441 [M+H] and elemental analysis indicated the molecular formula as $C_{30}H_{48}O_2$. Its IR absorption exhibited the presence of hydroxyl (3420 cm^{-1}) and double bond function (1640 cm^{-1}). In ^1H NMR spectrum, signals due to the six quaternary methyls at δ 0.75, 0.80, 0.95, 1.00, 1.19, 1.25, a doublet at δ 0.86 (J 6.3 Hz) for two secondary methyls indicated a tetracyclic triterpene skeleton of 1³. A two proton doublet of triplet at δ 4.95 (J 9.8, 5.7 Hz) and another two proton multiplet at δ 5.51 ($w_{1/2}$ 5.5 Hz) suggested two *cis*-oriented double bond functions in the compound. The presence of two disubstituted double bonds were further supported by ^{13}C NMR signals appearing at δ 125.3, 125.6, 126.1 and 126.3. In the ^{13}C NMR (DEPT) spectrum quaternary carbon signals at δ 133.4 and 134.2 indicated third double bond (tetrasubstituted) placed be-

tween C-8 and C-9. Formation of fragment ions at m/z 297 [M-side chain(Sc)]⁺, 295 [M-Sc-2H]⁴ resulting from the cleavage of side chain (m/z 143, $C_8H_{15}O_2^+$) and characteristic ion at m/z 255 generated due to the loss of side chain (Sc) with C-15, C-16, C-17 through internal hydrogen transfer from C-18^{5,6} indicated the presence of one disubstituted double bond and a tertiary hydroxyl function in the side chain and the second disubstituted double bond was placed between C-2 and C-3 which was assumed to be generated by the dehydration of hydroxyl group (biogenetically) placed at C-3. A double doublet, J 11, 5 Hz at δ 3.4 assigned for an oxymethine proton along with the significant α fission ions at m/z 43, 73, 367 and 397 placed the secondary hydroxyl at C-24. The prominent α -fission ions at m/z 73, 99, 341, 367 supported the location of the disubstituted double bond of the side chain in between C-22 and C-23. A quaternary carbon signal at δ 73.9 along with fragment ion peak at m/z 99, 143, 297 and 341 suggested a tertiary hydroxyl group placed at C-20. The (+) optical rotation and comparison of its spectral data with reported in literature for euphanes^{4,7-9} and related triterpenes^{6,10}, compound 1 was characterized as 20,24-dihydroxyeupha-2,8,22-triene (1).

Compound 2 was obtained as crystalline compound, m.p. 63 °C, had molecular ion peak at m/z 438 which along with elemental analysis supported the molecular formula $C_{28}H_{54}O_3$. The IR spectrum exhibited bands for hydroxyl (3420 cm^{-1}), carboxyl ($3500\text{--}2500$ and 1705

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cm^{-1}), double bond (1642 cm^{-1}). Its ^1H NMR spectrum exhibited a one proton multiplet at δ 3.6 ($w_{1/2}$ 7.2 Hz) for an oxymethylene proton and another two proton multiplet at δ 5.3 ($w_{1/2}$ 4.6 Hz) for olefinic protons that supported the presence of a secondary hydroxyl group and a disubstituted *cis*-oriented double bond¹¹ in **2**. In the MS of **2** characteristic a fission ions produced at m/z 87, 113, 325, 351 and β fission ions produced at m/z 73, 127, 311 and 365 located the disubstituted double bond between C-5 and C-6^{12,13}. Presence of strong ion at m/z 59, 379 and 409 located the position of the secondary hydroxyl group at C-26. A two proton triplet at δ 2.33 (J 6.6 Hz) was assigned for a methylene group in the ^1H NMR and fragment ions at m/z 44, 45, 393, 394 and characteristic ion at m/z 60 due to the McLafferty rearrangement¹⁴ indicated terminally located COOH group in **2**. In addition, the ^1H NMR spectrum exhibited a three protons triplet at δ 0.88 (J 7.6 Hz) was assigned for a terminal methyl group. In the MS, fragment ions at interval of 14 mass unit between 59 to 325 and 113 to 379 further supported the long chain nature of **2**. The above discussion along with the analysis of its ^{13}C NMR (DEPT) spectrum characterized compound **2** as 5(6)-ene,26-hydroxyoctacosanoic acid **2** which to our knowledge is not reported as yet.

Experimental

The bark of *B. serrata* along with some leaves and twigs were collected from Jhansi (Urai) division and were identified by Botany & Pharmacognosy Division, CIMAP, Lucknow where a voucher specimen has been deposited. The air dried and powdered bark (1.2 kg) was extracted with methanol : water (4 : 1). The aqueous methanol extract after concentration was fractionated with hexane and ethyl acetate. The column chromatography of hexane extract afforded five compounds. Elution with hexane : ethyl acetate mixtures in increasing polarity afforded 20,24-dihydroxyeupha-2,8,22-triene (**1**), 5(6)-ene,26-hydroxyoctacosanoic acid (**2**), α -amyrenol, β -sitosterol and acetyl β -boswellic acid.

Fractions (52-55) obtained from column chromatography of the hexane extract with hexane-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) provided an impure compound (200 mg) which on purification by prep. TLC, hexane-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) yielded viscous compound **1** (0.070 g); $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 7.2$ (c 1.0, CHCl_3); IR ν_{max} 3420, 2990, 2865, 1640, 1460, 1380, 1210 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) 0.75, 0.80 (3H each, s, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$), 0.86 (6H, d, J 6.3 Hz, H_3 -26, H_3 -27), 0.95, 1.00, 1.19, 1.25 (3H each, s, $4 \times \text{CH}_3$), 2.08 (6H, m, H_2 -1, H_2 -7, H_2 -11), 3.34 (1H, dd, J 11 and 5 Hz, H-24), 4.95 (2H, dt, J 9.8, 5.7 Hz, H-2, H-3 or H-22, H-23), 5.11 (2H, m, $w_{1/2}$ 5.5 Hz, H-22, H-23/H-2, H-3); ^{13}C NMR (DEPT, CDCl_3) δ 15.4, 15.6, 15.7, 19.2, 20.3, 21.5, 27.7, 28.7 ($8 \times \text{CH}_3$), 24.4, 25.7, 30.0, 35.7, 38.2, 39.2, 39.7 ($7 \times \text{CH}_2$), 36.5, 48.9, 51.3 ($3 \times \text{CH}$), 73.9 (C-20), 79.3 (C-24), 125.3, 125.6, 126.1, 126.3 ($2 \times \text{CH}=\text{CH}$), 133.4, 134.2 (C-8 and C-9); FAB-MS m/z 463 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$, 441 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$; EIMS m/z 440 $[\text{M}]^+$, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_2$ (18.2), 425 $[\text{M}-\text{CH}_3]^+$ (31.2), 422 $[\text{M}-\text{H}_2\text{O}]^+$ (5.3), 410 $[\text{M}-2 \times \text{CH}_3]^+$ (62.3), 407 $[\text{M}-\text{CH}_3-\text{H}_2\text{O}]^+$ (18.2), 404 $[\text{M}-2 \times \text{H}_2\text{O}]^+$ (7.2), 397 $[\text{M}-\text{C}_3\text{H}_7]^+$ (15.7), 367 $[\text{M}-\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{O}]^+$ (19.2), 341 $[\text{M}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{O}]^+$ (27.8), 297 $[\text{M}-\text{Sc}]^+$ (14.2), 295 $[\text{M}-\text{Sc}-2\text{H}]^+$ (11.3), 255 (22.3), 189 (37.2), 143 $[\text{Sc}, \text{C}_8\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2]^+$ (44.6), 125 $[\text{Sc}-\text{H}_2\text{O}]^+$ (12.4), 109 (100), 107 $[\text{Sc}-2 \times \text{H}_2\text{O}]^+$ (88.2), 99 (62.4), 73 (37.2), 43 (69.7) (Found : C, 81.73; H, 10.96. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_2$ requires : C, 81.75; H, 10.98%).

Fractions (56-65) obtained from column chromatography of hexane extract with hexane-ethyl acetate (17 : 3) provided crystalline compound **2** (0.105 g); m.p. 63° ; IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3420 (OH), 3500-2500, 2920, 2850, 1705 (COOH), 1642 (Δ), 1466, 1410, 1375, 1300 and 720 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ 0.88 (3H, t, J 7.6 Hz, terminal CH_3), 1.26 (36H, m, $18 \times \text{CH}_2$), 1.60 (4H, m, H_2 -25, H_2 -27), 2.02 (4H, m, H_2 -4, H_2 -7), 2.33 (2H, t, J 6.6

Chart 1. Mass fragmentation of compound **2**

Hz, H₂-2), 3.6 (1H, m, *w*_{1/2} 7.2 Hz, CHOH), 5.3 (2H, m, *w*_{1/2} 4.6 Hz, H-5, H-6); ¹³C NMR (DEPT, CDCl₃) δ 12.3 (CH₃), 20.9, 22.9, 27.4, 30.1, 32.2 (22 × CH₂), 63.4 (CHOH), 114, 128 (CH=CH), 179.4 (COOH); FAB-MS *m/z* 439 [M+H]⁺, EIMS *m/z* (rel. int.) 438 [M]⁺ (3.1) C₂₈H₅₄O₃, 424 [M-CH₂]⁺ (12.4), 423 [M-CH₃]⁺ (7.2), 409 [M-C₂H₅]⁺ (36.2), 394 [M-COO]⁺ (18.3), 393 [M-COOH]⁺ (12.7), 379 (22.1), 365 (8.1), 351 (16.2), 339 (18.3), 337 (9.1), 323 (5.2), 325 (29.4), 311 (16.8), 309 (9.4), 297 (3.1), 281 (3.7), 283 (6.4), 269 (8.1), 267 (7.4), 255 (3.6), 241 (4.5), 239 (9.1), 227 (7.3), 213 (9.2), 211 (11.2), 199 (6.4), 183 (7.2), 171 (8.1), 143 (7.2), 141 (3.7), 127 (4.3), 113 (27.6), 101 (11.4), 99 (26.2), 87 (26.1), 87 (44.2), 73 (12.3), 73 (26.7), 60 (26.4), 59 (47.2), 45 (31.5), 44 (17.8) (Found : C, 76.0; H, 12.39. C₂₈H₅₄O₃ requires : C, 76.64, H, 12.41%).

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